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THE MAIN INFLUENCERS OF THE QUALITY ASSURANCE IN TERTIARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: Globalization and advanced information technology have created competitive environment for education market, simplifying academic mobility process and affording every student to apply for it. In order to keep its market share educational establishments started developed different marketing technologies to create and strengthening own brand, where much attention is paid to the quality assurance of education service. Education quality service and influencers of this process in Uzbekistan and abroad has been considered in the article.

Keywords: Quality assurance, branding, quality of education service, assessment of students and teachers, internalization, academic mobility.

Annotatsiya: Globallashtiruv va ilg'or axborot texnologiyalari ta'lim bozorida raqobat muhitini yaratib, akademik mobillik jarayonini soddalashtirdi hamda har bir talabaga ushbu imkoniyatdan foydalanish imkonini berdi. O'z bozor ulushini saqlab qolish maqsadida ta'lim muassasalari turli marketing texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqib, o'z brendini yaratish va mustahkamlashga e'tibor qaratmoqda. Bunda ta'lim xizmatlari sifati kafolatiga alohida e'tibor berilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston va xorijda ta'lim xizmatlari sifati hamda ushbu jarayonga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: sifat kafolati, brending, ta'lim xizmatlari sifati, talabalar va o'qituvchilar baholash tizimi, internatsionalizatsiya, akademik mobillik.

Аннотация: Глобализация и передовые информационные технологии создали конкурентную среду на рынке образования, упростив процесс академической мобильности и предоставив каждому студенту возможность подать заявку на участие в нём. Чтобы сохранить свою долю рынка, образовательные учреждения начали разрабатывать различные маркетинговые технологии для создания и укрепления собственного бренда, уделяя особое внимание обеспечению качества образовательных услуг. В статье рассматриваются вопросы качества образовательных услуг и факторы, влияющие на этот процесс в Узбекистане и за рубежом.

Ключевые слова: обеспечение качества, брендинг, качество образовательных услуг, оценка студентов и преподавателей, интернационализация, академическая мобильность.

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, education, especially tertiary education, has always attracted significant attention among researchers, as it plays a crucial role in developing human capital—the most important factor in production. It is essential for creating all types of services and products necessary for human life.

Moreover, advancements in information and pedagogical technology have positioned tertiary education as a highly demanded service on the global stage. To operate high-tech systems effectively, employees need to be well-educated and highly qualified.

Examining the education market in Uzbekistan, one can clearly notice that the tertiary education sector follows an oligopoly market structure. Oligopoly, as a market structure with a small number of firms, has both advantages and disadvantages. One advantage is that consumers—students and their parents—may benefit from lower prices and better-quality education services and products. Furthermore, applicants and their parents are well-informed about available educational services due to rapid industrial development and globalization, which have expanded access to information and increased their ability to compare and choose among various options.

These recent changes have made consumers more concerned about the quality of education services and products. In the past, secondary school graduates and their parents primarily evaluated higher education institutions (HEIs) based on occupational perspectives. However, nowadays, they select educational services based on various economic indicators such as brand reputation, tuition fees, and other factors, as multiple similar providers operate in the market.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In order to attract consumers' attention and to survive in competitive market conditions, companies here HEI developed different brand strategies, where quality assurance became a key element. Economists tried to define this term differently, however most of them as Parasuraman, Wang and Shieh, Cetinã agreed that it certainly concerns with the expectations and perceptions of consumers about the merchandise exploited, and the activity of the manufacturer. While measuring the quality of goods, consumer can touch or feel and see its color, style, package, as the product he wants to buy as it is tangible, which somehow helps a consumer to have a notion about it by using certain feelings. Assessing the quality of service causes some difficulties, as intangibility makes difficult to evaluate consumers' perception of service quality, which may decrease provider's awareness about it.¹ That must be one of the most strong arguments why assessing the quality of education stays one of the most discussed and versatile issues nowadays, while here we should state that assessing the quality of a certain education establishment can be done both by management of HEI or appropriate state committee of the country and by consumers of the service who are interested in buying them.

Here, an effective system of quality management in higher education is based on a model (standard), which plays the role of referential or criteria system for external evaluation (quality assurance function), and a guide for the internal organization (management function quality). While assessing the quality of education service applicants mostly pay attention to the reputation and tuition fee of the service, while management of HEI cares about content (subjects taught), material resource and ways of delivery. One of the most important point here, we should always remember, that quality of the service differ according to the region and university itself, as we cannot compare education in Europe and developing countries, for example.

What is the most appropriate way to assess the quality of education service and what directions should be paid attention while assessing it and what measures should be taken in order to improve its state?

The role of Bologna process in assessing quality assurance, which aimed to set up European Higher Education Area was noted in the article "Quality Assurance In The European Higher Education Area" by İlker KEÇETEP*, İdil ÖZKAN². Firstly, the notion "education quality assurance" became an important issue during the Berlin Conference in 2003 and still stays keeping its urgency. According to their opinion, as development of higher education differs in different countries according its speed and way of improving, establishment of Quality assurance, certainly, takes much time and effort. Initially, it should be concentrated on making internal self-assessment of the Higher Education Institutions and figuring out weaknesses and strengths of the establishment and this one is only at national level, mentioning that Higher Education issue is under responsibility and authority of the State- government. Moreover, every country has to consider its own domestic needs and socio-economic position; higher education institutions should have a clear policy, written rules and quality standards for the assurance. There should be developed the culture of the evaluation process on the positive base professionally providing mutual recognition because there is a need for mutual trust – confidence. Authors also emphasize on teaching staff (must be well qualified, open to innovations, changes & new developments, criticism and evaluation), students' evaluation (should have a written format which explains the criteria of evaluation/grading and so on) and teaching-learning equipment and nice environment (HEI management).

1 2.Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., Berry, L.L. 1985 A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research, Journal of Marketing

2 Quality Assurance In The European Higher Education Area , İlker KEÇETEP*, İdil ÖZKAN August 2014, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences

Westerheijden D. F introduces a new approach to this topic in which the following elements in his opinion can be found: a) a process of self-evaluation. In some cases the assessment is limited to this element. This is especially the case when the assessment takes the form of an intrainstitutional review process; b) a review by peers, usually in the form of a visit by a team of external assessors; c) finally, especially in the U.S., these two elements are brought together in a wider system of accreditation in which (except for self-evaluation and review by peers) one other element is crucial: the formulation of standards that are used to make the decision to give or withhold accreditation.³

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study involves both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Data collection methods include surveys and structured interviews with university faculty, administrators, and students to assess key factors influencing quality assurance. Additionally, institutional reports and policy documents are analyzed to understand regulatory frameworks. The gathered data is processed using statistical analysis for quantitative insights, while qualitative responses undergo thematic analysis to identify patterns and key trends in tertiary education quality assurance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Studying both researches closely, it becomes clear that, although the education process evolves and improves year by year, the key influencers and suppliers of this service remain the same. Only the methods of delivering the process have been developed in line with advancements in information and pedagogical technology.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the main influencers of educational services include teachers, who are responsible for ensuring students acquire knowledge and experience by employing creative teaching methods; departments with teaching staff, which must investigate and update curricula and material resources; and management, which must seek ways to optimize tuition fees, IT resources, and the development of modern and comfortable campuses (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The main influencers of educational service⁴.

As we mentioned above with creative and well qualified teachers can lead learners to increase their knowledge by teaching how to start thinking critically and presenting own ideas in order to support own point of view, while departments and management provide material resources, equipment and environment, to implement the process and improve technical base of the HEI in order to create effective and motivating atmosphere for educators and learners, which is not less important. One of

³ Towards a General Model of Quality Assessment in Higher Education Author(s): Frans A. van Vught and Don F. Westerheijden, Higher Education, Vol. 28, No. 3 (Oct., 1994)

⁴ Author

the ordinarily traditional tasks of altering institutes of higher learning towards higher performance is effective leadership, as leaders are in the chairs of power and they influence and control financial, human, and other resources, also, they provide necessary support for greater accomplishments and victory⁵. If they work together to improve quality assurance, certainly earn learners' satisfaction and improving the quality of education quality without doubt.

While discussing a teachers' activity we should always remember the difference between traditional and modern teaching process, about its merits and demerits. Just as an example where in modern student-centered learning process, a teacher just guides to the world of idea and manages the world of knowledge⁶. However, effectiveness of his activity differs. As we know in conventional method a focus is on a teacher and he leads the process giving student's secondary place. While student centered process provides learners more creativity and independence in learning process, not every teacher's effectiveness is high, which causes continuing discussions about measure of assessing teachers' quality. What are the main influencers on teachers' effectiveness: years of experience, circumstances, material resources or flourishing conditions?

In the article "Do teachers' years of experience make a difference in the quality of teaching?" by Linda J. and others⁷ discussed teacher quality and influence the years of experience to the quality, by conducting classroom observation with the teachers from seven government primary schools in Queens-land, Australia. Authors analyzed the study in detail and suggest that there is no a big difference between beginning and experienced teachers, all teachers despite of age, place or other indicators need better support and professional learning. Table 1 illustrates the table which expresses authors' idea that the mean of differences between Beginning and Experienced in all directions is insignificant while transitioning's is lower, which proves authors idea (Table 1).

Table 1. Table of CLASS domains for three group analysis: Beginning, transitioning and experienced⁸.

CLASS Domain	Teacher Experience Category			F(2, 76)	P	ηp^2
	<i>Beginning (0–3 years) n = 25</i>	<i>Transitioning (4–5 years) n = 11</i>	<i>Experienced (+5 years) n = 44</i>			
	M ± SD	M ± SD	M ± SD			
<i>Emotional Support</i>	5.34 ± 0.97	4.72 ± 1.39	5.32 ± .76	1,604	0,208	0,04
<i>Classroom Organisation</i>	4.76 ± 1.36	4.26 ± 1.40	5.14 ± 1.07	3,296	0,042	0,08
<i>Instructional Support</i>	3.39 ± 1.19	3.18 ± 1.34	3.84 ± .96	2,6	0,081	0,06

In the article, two types of questionnaires—one for students and one for teachers—were prepared for data collection. After reviewing all responses and identifying key problems and solutions, a plan was created to provide a foundation for future work in this area, aiming to establish a clear and simple approach for implementation.

According to this plan, in order to ensure pedagogical quality, an educational institution should focus on the following aspects:

- 5 Entrepreneurial leadership for university leaders: A futuristic approach for Pakistani HEIs, Abdul Wahab, IrmaTyasari, Asia Pacific Management Review Volume 25, Issue 1, March 2020, Pages 54-63
- 6 Quality management in higher education services, Bogdanel Marian Draguta, Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences 15 (2011) 3366–3368)
- 7 Do teachers' years of experience make a difference in the quality of teaching?, Teaching and Teacher Education Volume 96, November 2020
- 8 Do teachers' years of experience make a difference in the quality of teaching?, Teaching and Teacher Education Volume 96, November 2020

Effective administration, responsible for student admissions, ICT development, and the provision of services for transversal skills (such as certified language programs and computer literacy).

Competent teachers, who must undergo mandatory and continuous training while adopting the best didactical practices.

A well-equipped library, which preserves and promotes a shared digital heritage while assisting both students and staff.

Adequate facilities and industry collaboration, including resource centers for teachers and strong university-enterprise relationships that facilitate student internships and improve employability.

These findings reaffirm the article's main argument that, despite the advancements in information and pedagogical technology, the core suppliers of education remain unchanged: teachers, management, and academic departments.

Quality Assurance of Education in Uzbekistan

Regarding the quality assurance of educational services in Uzbekistan, the educational process can be divided into four historical periods:

Before the Soviet Union

The early decades of the Soviet Union

The late 20th century (1980s and beyond)

After gaining independence (1991–present)

During the medieval period, Uzbekistan was historically known as Turkestan, Movarounnahr, or Turon, and this era is often referred to as the country's "golden age" due to the flourishing education system and renowned scholars such as Al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, and Al-Farabi. Students from across the world traveled to Bukhara and Samarkand to complete seven- or eight-year training programs, making these cities early examples of academic mobility. At the time, Arabic was the primary language of instruction. Uzbekistan's education system was highly competitive, producing scholars who made significant contributions to global civilization before returning to their homeland with vast knowledge reserves.

By the late 19th century, Russia had conquered Central Asia, incorporating the territories of the Khanates of Bukhara and Khiva, as well as parts of the Fergana Valley (formerly part of the Khanate of Kokand), into what later became the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic.

During the early 20th century, a reformist movement called "Usul-i Jadid" (New Method) emerged in Central Asia. This movement significantly influenced education during the initial decades of the Soviet era and later resurfaced after Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991 (Uzbekistan, 2015). While the Soviet period brought technical progress and improved literacy rates, the collapse of the USSR created financial constraints, making it difficult to sustain and modernize educational structures, infrastructure, textbooks, teaching methods, and curricula. Foreign aid has been essential, but insufficient to compensate for the loss of centralized funding.

Under the Soviet Union, Russian served as the lingua franca across all socialist republics. As a result, until 1991, many Uzbek families preferred Russian-language schools for their children. Since all educational institutions were government-owned, there was no competition, leading to a decline in the quality of education. The internationalization of education began to take shape in the 1980s.

With Uzbekistan's independence in 1991, the country entered a new phase. The newly sovereign state adopted internationalization strategies in higher education, aligning educational trends and policies with national interests. Post-independence, the government prioritized improving the education system by fostering competition through private and foreign educational institutions. However, for many years, an oligopoly system dominated the sector, which adversely affected the quality of education services.

The Concept of Higher Education Development in Uzbekistan by 2030 adopted on 8 October 2019 describes the strategy of the HE development and clarified the main goals of the HEIs. Two new Law on Education and Law on Science have been adopted in 2020. The new Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education adopted in 2020 introduced for the first time the concept of inclusive education, considered dual education with work placement and distance education as one of the

forms of education implemented through ICT and Internet⁹. Uzbekistan has been focusing on raising the education system to a global level by strengthening international cooperation. It is also stated in The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan that in minimum 10 universities of the state should have an international rating¹⁰ and participation in the process of world education is one of the key factors to achieve success.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Quality of education service has always been attracted attention among scholars, as it deals with the most important factor- teaching and preparing labor force, who intends to be responsible for creation of any kinds of service, product or information in near future. Being intangible assessment of services causes difficulties, as a potential customer cannot use his feeling as seeing or touching.

Due to the rapid development of IT and globalization academic mobility became affordable, which make management of HEI to care keeping its market share in the education market and expand its own business, where creation and development of brand became a key element. The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan also pays much attention to improve quality of education service and adopted several decrees and regulations. Increasing internalization and academic mobility are also meant to be sufficient ways to provide perfect competition in the sphere, which is beneficial for consumers and suppliers, here students and HEI.

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